

FORWARD Brand for OR research

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A brand for OR research

During the first months of activity, the ITC created the brand for OR research, to be used during and after the project. The purpose of this brand is to identify research produced in the Outermost Regions.

The brand for OR research is complementary to the visual identity of the project and it will not substitute it.

1 Graphic symbol

The ITC made three proposals for the selection of the Forward brand for OR research, inspired in the existing graphic symbol of the quality of agricultural and fishery products of the Outermost Regions¹.

¹ <https://www.gobiernodecanarias.org/agricultura/icca/servicios/simbolorup/>

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Following a selection process, the partners selected a graphic symbol based on FORWARD logo. Other proposals, finally not selected, are included in annex 1.

2 How to use the OR research brand?

The OR research brand will be initially used by the regional institutions that participate in FORWARD project, both as partners or stakeholders, in their communication material such as websites, posters, leaflets, tailored info sheets on research topics/activities of excellence in ORs, etc.

In particular, the OR research brand will be used in the production of promotional and communication material (leaflets, brochures, etc) for research groups from ORs that will participate in networking activities under WP5. Such material will be designed and produced in the framework of the project.

The specific rules for the use of the OR research brand will be proposed during the development of WP5 activities and will need the approval of the Steering Committee

The OR research brand will be available for its use after the end of the project.

Annex 1: Initial proposals. Brand for OR research.

OPTION 1

Option 1: It represents an adaptation of Outermost Regions Logo to the R+D+i. The circle changes into a light bulb (as innovation symbol) with an arrow, which represents the leadership opportunities on this sector. On the same way, waves take the form of a growing graphic representation.

OPTION 2

Option 2: It represents a sailboat guided by the 9 stars representing the push of the outermost regions union. In the sail, the icon of a microscope symbolizing the importance of the science for these regions.

OPTION 3

Option 3: a triangle including a gear represents the capacity of the regions to drive new projects in R+D+i. The gear forms an eye (most evident in monochrome designs) which could mean the necessary vision to discover the opportunities of these territories. Under, 2 waves represent the sea as union between the outermost regions.